

Original Article

Indigenous Development and Psychometric Evaluation of the Negative and Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage Questionnaire (NPBAM-Q)

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Abstract

The current study aimed to develop and validate the Negative and Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage Questionnaire (NPBAM-Q), an indigenous tool to assess both negative and positive beliefs about arranged marriage within Pakistan's cultural context. The development process followed rigorous psychometric procedures, including item generation through a literature review and qualitative interviews, followed by thematic analysis and expert evaluations to ensure content validity. The finalized questionnaire included two subscales: Negative Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (NBAM) and Positive Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (PBAM). Data were collected from 312 participants (156 males, 156 females) aged 18 to 35 years, using convenience sampling. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) confirmed a two-factor structure, explaining 52.25% of the cumulative variance. Reliability analysis indicated strong internal consistency ($\alpha = .90$ for NBAM and $\alpha = .86$ for PBAM). Discriminant validity was established through a significant negative correlation between NBAM and PBAM. The gender comparison revealed that women held more negative beliefs about arranged marriage, while no significant gender differences were found in positive beliefs about arranged marriage. These findings support the NPBAM-Q as a reliable and culturally sensitive instrument for assessing both negative and positive beliefs about arranged marriage.

Keywords: Arranged Marriage, Negative and Positive Beliefs, Questionnaire Development, Validation

Introduction

Marriage is one of the most influential social institutions, impacting individuals' psychological development, family systems, social structures, and cultural continuity (Myers et al., 2018). In particular, the type and structure of marriage — whether arranged or love-based—shape expectations, relational roles, and long-term satisfaction. In collectivist cultures such as Pakistan, arranged marriage remains the predominant form of marital union, where decisions regarding spouse selection are often taken by elders or family members based on compatibility, familial values, and cultural preservation (Zaidi & Shuraydi, 2019). Arranged marriages are historically rooted in the belief that parents and elders possess the life experience and foresight required to make sound decisions on behalf of their children. In such societies, the institution of marriage is viewed not just as a romantic partnership, but as a strategic familial alliance one that fortifies social ties, ensures intergenerational continuity, and maintains socio-economic status (Hussain & Bittles, 2017).

Researchers have emphasized that, in Pakistan and other collectivist cultures, arranged marriages are seen as enhancing family honor, minimizing risk, and maintaining ethnic and religious boundaries (Israr et al., 2020). Yet, beliefs about arranged marriages are neither universal nor uniformly positive. While many people value the structure, support, and family involvement that comes with arranged marriages, others see them differently as a way to control personal choices, especially when it comes to women (Hassan, 2019). These concerns often come from lived experiences, growing access to modern education, changing ideas about gender roles, and exposure to global media that emphasize independence and love-based relationships (Ahmed, 2021).

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Interestingly, research shows that younger, urban Pakistanis are now leaning toward more flexible approaches to marriage models that combine both family input and individual choice (Ishfaq, Nawaz, & Saddique, 2022). Our beliefs about arranged marriage can deeply influence how we view ourselves, how we relate emotionally, and how we connect across generations. People who view arranged marriage positively often feel more supported by their families, experience stronger family harmony, and are generally more satisfied with their match (Ali et al., 2020). On the flip side, those who hold more critical views of arranged marriage may deal with feelings of dissatisfaction, pressure to conform, or a loss of personal freedom issues that can lead to emotional stress or even problems within the marriage itself (Hassan, 2019). These psychological effects don't impact everyone the same way they can vary depending on someone's gender, financial background, life experiences, or even how their marriage turns out in the end.

Zaidi and Shuraydi (2019) found that many Pakistani women face emotional struggles as they try to meet traditional expectations while also chasing modern dreams. While some may believe arranged marriage provides safety and stability, others quietly fear the consequences of not having a say in such a life-altering decision (Israr et al., 2020). Cultural psychology suggests that our attitudes toward marriage aren't formed in isolation. They're shaped by the world around us through things like gender norms, class systems, religion, and legal traditions. Hofstede's (2001) theory on cultural dimensions also helps explain why arranged marriages continue to thrive in collectivist societies like Pakistan, where values such as family unity, respect for elders, and social interdependence are deeply rooted. These values don't just shape how people choose to marry they also influence how they view their roles and responsibilities once they're married.

Another useful lens is the Social Exchange Theory (Homans, 1958), which says that people often weigh the benefits and drawbacks when forming relationships. In arranged marriages, families tend to think beyond just emotional compatibility. They also consider practical factors like financial security, social respect, and long-term family alliances. This pragmatic mindset supports the belief common in collectivist cultures that love can grow after marriage, even if it wasn't there from the start (Ahmed, 2021).

Despite the central role arranged marriage plays in many cultures, there is still a lack of understanding of regarding the specific beliefs surrounding it. Most studies focus on what happens after marriage like divorce, fertility, or satisfaction without really exploring the deeper emotional and thought patterns that influence how people see marriage in the first place. This represents a significant gap, as beliefs influence every stage: before agreeing to the marriage, during it, and even in how people reflect on it afterward.

Recent research also highlights the dynamic nature of belief systems around arranged marriages (Ishfaq, Nawaz, & Saddique, 2022), for instance, discovered that young adults in urban Pakistan who supported arranged marriage also anticipated gender equality, emotional ties, and mutual consent. These results point to a trend toward what some scholars refer to as "modern-traditional blends" or hybrid marriage models, in which individual choice and family engagement coexist. The creation of psychometrically valid, culturally relevant measures is essential in light of these changes. Counselors, educators, and policymakers find it challenging to comprehend the internal belief conflicts that people have when juggling the demands of modernity and tradition in the absence of standardized instruments. In addition to providing information for pre-marital counseling, family mediation, and social awareness campaigns, measuring both positive and negative views might help specialists anticipate which people may experience harmony versus unhappiness in arranged marriages.

The idea that parents and elders have the knowledge and insight required to make wise choices for their children's futures has historically been the foundation of arranged marriages in Pakistan (Israr et al., 2020). This practice strengthens social relationships, ensures intergenerational continuity, and maintains socioeconomic position; it is not just a union between two people but a strategic alliance between families (Hussain & Bittles, 2017). These marriages, which reflect ingrained cultural traditions, frequently place emphasis on elements like caste, religious compatibility, and family reputation (Ali, Rehman, & Niazi, 2020).

Even though arranged weddings are common in Pakistan, little is known about the particular belief systems that influence people's decisions and attitudes toward this custom. Although instruments such as the Future Positive Core Beliefs Scale (FPBS) have been created to evaluate general optimistic attitudes (Akbar et al., 2025), there are still few culturally based tools that look at ideas regarding arranged marriage in particular. Due to a lack of native resources, many people are forced to make a significant life decision between an arranged marriage and a love marriage without fully comprehending how their internalized beliefs affect that decision.

In many parts of the world, especially in Western countries like those in Europe and North America, arranged marriage is often viewed quite differently from how it is understood in Pakistan. There, marriage is usually seen as a personal decision something based on love, emotional connection, and individual freedom (Myers et al., 2018). In contrast, arranged marriages are sometimes misrepresented as being forced or lacking in choice. Penn (2011) points out that this view doesn't always reflect reality, especially among immigrant communities in the West where arranged marriages still exist but often involve the consent of both partners. These families tend to value tradition while also allowing their children a say in the process, creating a kind of balance between old and new values. Netting (2010) calls this a "modern-traditional blend," where people try to respect cultural expectations while also prioritizing personal compatibility and equality. These global differences show how beliefs about arranged marriage are shaped by larger social values like independence in the West and family obligations in collectivist cultures like Pakistan. Bringing in this wider perspective helps us better understand the complex ways people form beliefs about marriage, and why developing culturally grounded tools to study those beliefs is so important.

To examine both negative and positive attitudes toward arranged marriage in Pakistan, the current study intends to create and validate an indigenous questionnaire. It integrates empirical research, cultural theory, and psychological insight to create a robust framework for future studies. This tool is designed not only for academic exploration but also for practical application in clinical, educational, and cultural settings.

Objectives

1. To develop an indigenous questionnaire to assess beliefs about arranged marriage in the Pakistani cultural context.
2. To determine the psychometric properties (reliability and validity) of the developed questionnaire.
3. To explore the association between negative and positive beliefs about arranged marriage.
4. To examine the gender-specific difference in negative and positive beliefs about arranged marriage.

Hypotheses

- It is expected that there will be a negative relationship between positive and negative beliefs about arranged marriage.
- It is anticipated that women will report higher levels of negative beliefs about arranged marriage compared to men.

Method

The development and validation of the Negative and Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage Questionnaire (NPBAM-Q) was carried out in two phases. Phase 1 incorporated item development including item generation, content validation, and piloting; however, Phase II included determining validation and psychometric properties of the newly developed measure. As suggested by Carpenter (2017), scale development is most effective when it follows a systematic process that includes theoretical grounding, item refinement through expert feedback, and psychometric evaluation using appropriate statistical techniques. These steps were closely followed in the current study to enhance the quality and robustness of the final instrument.

Phase 1: Item Development

Phase I was proposed to develop the item development and consisted of two steps. The first step was intended to generate an item pool for scale with the help of young university students, old people, and experts by using open-ended questionnaires. Hence the item pool was generated.

Step 1: Construct Identification and Item Generation

To develop a culturally relevant questionnaire assessing beliefs about arranged marriage, an exploratory qualitative phase was conducted to identify key constructs. The process involved semi-structured interviews with a purposive sample of 15 participants, including five psychology professionals, five university students, and five senior citizens. These participants were selected to represent diverse age groups and perspectives on arranged marriage. Open-ended questions were asked to explore their views on the positive and negative beliefs about arranged marriages.

Interviews were audio-recorded with consent and transcribed verbatim. Thematic analysis was employed to analyze the data, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) guidelines. Several prominent themes emerged from the data, including stability, family involvement and support, pressure and loss of autonomy, emotional disconnection,

compatibility concerns, and respect for tradition. These themes were used as the foundational constructs for item development.

Based on these emergent themes and a thorough literature review (e.g., Zaidi & Shuraydi, 2002; Holtzworth-Munroe, 2007), an initial pool of 38 items was generated to reflect both positive with 17 items and negative beliefs with 21 items about arranged marriage. Items were written in clear and culturally appropriate language in both English and Urdu to ensure comprehension.

To ensure the content truly reflected what it aimed to measure, a panel of ten experts in cultural studies and psychology carefully reviewed the questionnaire items. They looked at each question to see if it matched the intended concept, was worded, and made sense within the cultural context. Based on their feedback, a few items that seemed confusing or unnecessary were taken out, while others were rewritten to improve clarity and cultural sensitivity. After a thorough review process, 25 items were finalized for pilot testing and factor structure evaluation, including 11 items for positive beliefs about arranged marriage and 14 items for negative beliefs about arranged marriage.

Step 2: Try-Out (Pilot Testing)

Next, a small group of 20 participants 10 men and 10 women took part in a pilot study to test the revised questionnaire. They came from different walks of life, including both community members and college students. After filling out the questionnaire, they shared their thoughts on how easy it was to understand, how relevant the questions felt, and whether the response options made sense. Based on their feedback, a few minor wording adjustments were made to make the items clearer and easier to follow. In the final version, each belief statement was rated using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 meant “Strongly Disagree” and 5 meant “Strongly Agree.”

Phase 2: Determining Psychometric Properties of the Questionnaire

Phase II of scale development was to run a factor analysis, determine the scoring procedure, and conduct a reliability analysis. Factor analysis was used to identify the underlying factor structure of the items in the final NPBAM-Q scale. Percentile ranks were employed to establish cut-off points, and a reliability analysis was conducted to evaluate the internal consistency using alpha coefficient. Following the factor analysis and reliability assessment, the scale underwent a refinement process to ensure psychometric soundness. From the initial pool of 25 items (11 assessing positive beliefs and 14 assessing negative beliefs), only those items demonstrating strong factor loadings and satisfactory corrected item-total correlations were retained. As a result, the finalized version of the NPBAM-Q consisted of 19 items in which 8 items measuring positive beliefs and 11 items measuring negative beliefs about arranged marriage. The internal consistency of the refined scale was subsequently re-evaluated and found to be within acceptable reliability thresholds. The finalized items are presented in the appendix for reference.

Sample

For the psychometric evaluation, a total of 312 participants were selected using purposive sampling. The sample consisted of 156 males and 156 females, with an age range of 18 to 35 years and a mean age of 22.37 years (SD = 3.91). Participants represented both urban (78.5%) and rural (21.5%) areas of Pakistan. Educational levels ranged from undergraduate to postgraduate students, ensuring a literate population capable of understanding the questionnaire content.

Procedure

Participants were briefed about the purpose of the research and ensured confidentiality and voluntary participation. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before their inclusion in the study. The questionnaire was administered in both individual and group formats, depending on the setting, which included academic institutions and community centers. Data collection took approximately 5-10 minutes per participant. Trained data collectors were present to provide assistance if needed, especially in community settings. No personally identifying information was collected to maintain anonymity.

Results

Construct validity was examined by conducting PCA with Varimax rotation. Several assumptions were empirically examined to make sure data were usable for factor analysis. Several approaches have been identified by researchers for evaluating sampling adequacy, and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure is probably the most commonly used. Kaiser (1960) suggests a minimum value KMO for an adequate sample is .50 (.50 to .70 =

mediocre, .70 to .80 = good, .80 to .90 = great and above .90 = superb). The KMO value of the current analysis was .90, thus confirming the sample adequacy was excellent. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was highly significant, $\chi^2 = 2714.88$, $***p < .001$, which suggested that the correlation among the items was strong enough to warrant going ahead with PCA (Hutcheson & Sofroniou, 1999).

Table 1

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test for Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (N = 312)

Kaiser- Mayers-Olkin Test for Sampling Adequacy	.90
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, Approx. χ^2	2714.88 ***
Df	17

Note. df= degree of freedom, $***p < .001$

Figure 1

The Scree Plot Derived from the Exploratory Factor Analysis Confirmed a Two-Factor Structure of the NPBAM-Q(N=312)

Figure 1 illustrates the scree plot generated from the factor analysis of the 19-item scale. The curve shows a steep drop in eigenvalues after the second component, forming a noticeable "elbow," which suggests a clear break between meaningful and less meaningful factors. The first two components have much higher eigenvalues compared to the rest, indicating that they account for a significant portion of the variance in the data. Beyond the second component, the line begins to flatten out, with the remaining components contributing very little. This pattern supports the decision to retain two factors, as components after the second are likely capturing noise rather than meaningful structure.

Table 2

Factor Structure and Item Analysis for Negative and Positive Beliefs About Arranged Marriage Questionnaire (N = 312)

Sr. #	Item Code	Item Statement	Factor 1	Factor 2	r ^{it}
1	NBAM3	ارینج میریج میں زندگی اپنی مرضی سے نہیں گزارا جا سکتی ہے۔	.72	.03	.70**
2	NBAM4	ارینج میریج میں زندگی مشکل ہوتی ہے۔	.69	-.08	.69**
3	NBAM5	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ایک دوسرے سے مطابقت نہیں رکھتے ہیں۔	.69	-.05	.69**
4	NBAM6	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ہر بات شیئر نہیں کر سکتے ہیں۔	.73	-.07	.74**
5	NBAM 7	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ایک دوسرے کا ساتھ نہیں دیتے ہیں۔	.62	-.23	.65**

Sr. #	Item Code	Item Statement	Factor 1	Factor 2	r ^{it}
6	NBAM8	ارینج میریج میں ایک طرفہ کوششیں زیادہ ہوتی ہیں۔	.72	.00	.72**
7	NBAM9	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی مجبوری میں ساتھ رہتے ہیں۔	.74	-.13	.75**
8	NBAM11	ارینج میریج میں ذہنی سکون کم ہوتا ہے۔	.78	-.13	.79**
9	NBAM 12	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ایک دوسرے کو قبول نہیں کرتے ہیں۔	.64	-.17	.66**
10	NBAM13	ارینج میریج صرف خاندان والوں کو خوش رکھنے کے لیے کی جاتی ہے۔	.70	-.05	.70**
11	NBAM14	ارینج میریج میں لڑائی جھگڑے زیادہ ہوتے ہیں۔	.70	-.14	.71**
12	PBAM 1	رینج میرج میں گھر والوں کا ساتھ ہوتا ہے۔	.04	.63	.62**
13	PBAM4	ارینج میرج زیادہ کامیاب ہوتی ہے۔	-.15	.72	.73**
14	PBAM5	ارینج میرج میں زندگی زیادہ اچھی گزرتی ہے۔	-.25	.70	.74**
15	PBAM 6	والدین اپنی اولاد کے لئے صحیح جیون ساتھی تلاش کرتے ہیں۔	-.15	.64	.67**
16	PBAM7	ارینج میرج تمام پہلوؤں کو دیکھ کر کی جاتی ہے۔	-.14	.72	.74**
17	PBAM8	ارینج میرج میں میاں بیوی ایک دوسرے کا زیادہ احترام کرتے ہیں۔	-.15	.73	.74**
18	PBAM9	ارینج میرج میں خاندانی رسم و رواج پروان چڑھتے ہیں۔	-.02	.75	.74**
19	PBAM10	ارینج میرج میں ماں باپ کی عزت زیادہ کی جاتی ہے۔	.05	.79	.76**
Eigen Value			6.43	3.49	
% of Variance			33.84	18.41	
Cumulative %			33.84	52.25	

Note. All items had loadings > .60 on their primary factor and item-total correlations (r^{it}) > .60. Factor 1 = Negative Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (NBAM); Factor 2 = Positive Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (PBAM), **p<.001.

Factor Description

Exploratory factor analysis using principal axis factoring with varimax rotation was conducted on the 19 items of the Beliefs About Arranged Marriage Questionnaire. The analysis yielded a clear two-factor structure, explaining a cumulative 52.25% of the total variance, with Factor 1 (Negative Beliefs About Arranged Marriage) accounting for 33.84%, and Factor 2 (Positive Beliefs About Arranged Marriage) accounting for an additional 18.41% of the variance. The resulting two factors were identified and described as follows:

Factor 1: Negative Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (NBAM)

This factor captures the more critical or unfavorable views that people may hold about arranged marriages. A total of eleven items NBAM3, NBAM4, NBAM5, NBAM6, NBAM7, NBAM8, NBAM9, NBAM11, NBAM12, NBAM13, and NBAM14 loaded strongly on this factor. These items reflect concerns like lack of emotional connection, forced companionship, limited personal choice, and pressure from family or culture. Respondents who agree with these statements are more likely to feel that arranged marriages can be emotionally distant, difficult, or even burdensome. The factor loadings for these items were quite strong, ranging from .62 to .78, which shows that these items are closely tied to the negative belief dimension. The item-total correlations (r^{it} values) were also solid, between .65 and .79, suggesting that the items work well together and measure a consistent underlying idea. For example, the (There is less mental peace in arranged marriages) had one of the highest loadings at .78 and a r^{it} of .79, making it one of the strongest indicators of this factor. Similarly, (Spouses stay together out of compulsion) also stood out with loading of .74 and r^{it} of .75, reinforcing the negative perception theme.

Factor 2: Positive Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (PBAM)

In contrast, this factor highlights the positive and culturally valued aspects of arranged marriages. Eight items PBAM1, PBAM4, PBAM5, PBAM6, PBAM7, PBAM8, PBAM9, and PBAM10 loaded clearly on this factor. These items focus on ideas like family support, mutual respect between spouses, long-term success, and preservation of traditions. Participants who agreed with these statements likely believe that arranged marriages are thoughtful, respectful, and backed by the wisdom and involvement of the family. The factor loadings for this set of items ranged from .63 to .79, suggesting a strong relationship with the positive beliefs factor. The r^{it} values also

ranged from .62 to .76, indicating good consistency among the items. For example, (Parents are more respected in arranged marriages) had the highest loading at .79, and a r^2 of .76, making it a strong representation of this belief. Another key item, (Spouses in arranged marriages respect each other more), had a loading of .73 and r^2 of .74, further emphasizing the respect and harmony associated with positive arranged marriage experiences.

Reliability and Item Analysis

Table 3

Inter-Item Correlation of Negative Beliefs about Arrange Marriage(N=312)

Items	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
NBAM3	2.87	1.09	-	.51**	.45**	.46**	.41**	.50**	.44**	.51**	.35**	.48**	.40**
NBAM4	2.69	1.04		-	.57**	.51**	.43**	.46**	.41**	.50**	.33**	.35**	.41**
NBAM5	2.63	1.04			-	.52**	.45**	.46**	.46**	.44**	.38**	.29**	.39**
NBAM6	2.72	1.16				-	.52**	.56**	.46**	.53**	.38**	.43**	.38**
NBAM7	2.36	1.03					-	.44**	.44**	.42**	.39**	.27**	.39**
NBAM8	2.86	1.17						-	.49**	.48**	.36**	.44**	.37**
NBAM9	2.53	1.09							-	.61**	.51**	.55**	.54**
NBAM11	2.74	1.09								-	.52**	.58**	.59**
NBAM12	2.26	.94									-	.47**	.53**
NBAM13	2.93	1.25										-	.58**
NBAM14	2.50	1.02											-

Note. ** $p < .001$

Table 3 displays the inter-item correlations for the 11 items assessing Negative Beliefs about Arranged Marriage (NBAM), based on responses from 312 participants. The average item scores ranged from 2.26 to 2.93, with standard deviations between 0.94 and 1.25, showing a reasonable spread in how people answered. All the items were positively and significantly correlated with one another at *** $p < .001$, with correlation values falling between .27 and .61. The strongest relationship was seen between NBAM9 and NBAM11 ($r = .61$), suggesting these two items tap into very similar concerns. Overall, the pattern of moderate to strong correlations across the matrix supports the idea that these items reliably captured a common underlying belief system about arranged marriage.

Table 4

Inter-Item Correlation of Positive Beliefs about Arrange Marriage(N=312)

Items	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PBAM1	4.22	.94	-	.35**	.30**	.38**	.39**	.26**	.46**	.45**
PBAM4	3.53	.96		-	.62**	.42**	.42**	.55**	.42**	.45**
PBAM5	3.30	.96			-	.39**	.51**	.57**	.41**	.44**
PBAM6	3.80	.92				-	.49**	.36**	.39**	.44**
PBAM7	3.71	1.04					-	.49**	.45**	.49**
PBAM8	3.60	1.02						-	.53**	.50**
PBAM9	3.88	.92							-	.60**
PBAM10	3.66	1.01								-

Note. ** $p < .001$

Table 4 shows the inter-item correlations for the items that make up the Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage (PBAM) subscale, based on responses from 312 participants. The average item scores fell between 3.30 and 4.22, with standard deviations ranging from 0.92 to 1.04, which reflects a fair amount of variation in how participants responded. All of the items were positively and significantly correlated with one another at *** $p < .001$, with correlation values ranging from .26 to .62. This pattern suggests that the items were measuring a common

underlying concept and worked well together as a group. Notably, the strongest link was found between PBAM4 and PBAM5 ($r = .62$), showing that participants who agreed with one of these statements were very likely to agree with the other as well.

Table 5

Correlation of Negative and Positive Beliefs about Arrange Marriage (N=312)

Items	M	SD	1	2
NBAM	29.71	5.64	-	-.26 **
PBAM	29.10	8.56		-

Note. ** $p < .01$

Table 5 presents the correlation between the two subscales: Negative Beliefs about Arranged Marriage (NBAM) and Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage (PBAM), based on data from 312 participants. The average score on the NBAM was 29.10 (SD = 8.56), while the PBAM had a mean of 29.71 (SD = 5.64). A significant negative correlation was found between the two subscales ($r = -.26$, ** $p < .01$), suggesting that participants who endorsed stronger negative beliefs about arranged marriage were less likely to hold positive beliefs, and vice versa. This inverse relationship supports the idea that the two subscales capture opposing perspectives on the same underlying construct.

Table 6

Descriptive statistics and Reliability Analysis of Negative and Positive Beliefs about Arrange Marriage Questionnaire (N=312)

Scale	k	M	SD	Range	α	Skewness	Kurtosis
NBAM	11	29.10	8.56	11-55	.90	.35	-13
PBAM	8	29.71	5.64	8-40	.86	-.64	.95

Note. N= Number of participants, NBAM=Negative Beliefs about Arrange Marriage, PBAM=Positive Beliefs about Arrange Marriage, α =Cronbach's Alpha.

Table 6 provides descriptive statistics and reliability coefficients for the two subfactors identified through factor analysis: Negative Beliefs about Arranged Marriage (NBAM) and Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage (PBAM), based on responses from a sample of 312 participants. The NBAM subfactor, which includes 11 items, had a mean score of 29.10 (SD = 8.56), with a possible score range from 11 to 55. It showed high internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of .90, and the distribution was slightly positively skewed (skewness = .35) with a somewhat flatter shape (kurtosis = -1.3), suggesting a leptokurtic distribution. The PBAM subfactor, comprising 8 items, had a mean of 29.71 (SD = 5.64), with scores ranging from 8 to 40. It also demonstrated strong reliability ($\alpha = .86$), and the distribution showed a slight negative skew (skewness = -.64) along with moderate kurtosis (.95). These results reflect that both subfactors are internally consistent and statistically distinct, supporting their validity as separate dimensions within the broader construct of beliefs about arranged marriage.

Gender Norms of NPBAMQ

Table 7

Independent Sample t-test of Negative and Positive Beliefs about Arrange Marriage (N=312)

Analysis	Male (n=156)		Female (n=156)		t (310)	P	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
NBAM	27.54	8.54	30.65	8.32	-3.25	.001	-4.98	-1.22	-.36
PBAM	29.17	6.13	30.24	5.07	-1.68	.09	-2.32	.18	-.19

Note. NBAM= Negative Beliefs about Arrange Marriage, PBAM= Positive Beliefs about Arrange Marriage, CI= Confidence Interval, UL= Upper Limit, LL= Lower Limit, *** $p < .001$

Table 7 presents the results of independent samples t-tests comparing males (n = 156) and females (n = 156) on the two subscales of the Beliefs About Arranged Marriage Questionnaire: Negative Beliefs (NBAM) and Positive Beliefs (PBAM). The analysis indicated a statistically significant difference in negative beliefs about arranged marriage (NBAM) between male and female participants. Females (M = 30.65, SD = 8.32) reported significantly

higher negative beliefs than males ($M = 27.54$, $SD = 8.54$), $t(310) = -3.25$, $p = .001$. The 95% confidence interval for the mean difference ranged from -4.98 to -1.22 . The effect size, Cohen's $d = -0.36$, suggests a small to moderate effect, indicating that females in the sample were more likely to hold unfavorable views regarding arranged marriage.

In contrast, gender differences in positive beliefs about arranged marriage (PBAM) were not statistically significant. Although females ($M = 30.24$, $SD = 5.07$) scored slightly higher than males ($M = 29.17$, $SD = 6.13$), the difference did not reach the conventional level of significance, $t(310) = -1.68$, $p = .09$. The 95% confidence interval ranged from -2.32 to 0.18 , and the effect size (Cohen's $d = -0.19$) was small, suggesting minimal practical difference in positive beliefs between genders.

Scoring Procedure

The final questionnaire included two subscales: Negative Beliefs about Arranged Marriage (NBAM) and Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage (PBAM). Each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale. Scores are summed per subscale. Higher scores on PBAM indicate stronger positive beliefs, while higher NBAM scores reflect stronger negative beliefs.

Table 8

Cut-off Scores and Levels of Negative Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (NBAM)

Raw Score	Range	Percentile	Level	<i>f</i> (%)
<22	11 – 21	<25	Minimal NB	50(16)
28	22 – 27	50	Moderate NB	96(30)
35	28 – 34	75	Strong NB	97(31)
>35	35 – 55	>75	Firm NB	69(22)

Note. NB= Negative Beliefs

Table 8 presents the cut-off scores and corresponding levels for the Negative Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (NBAM) subscale. To categorize responses meaningfully, the score ranges were divided into four equal intervals based on quartiles. The 25th percentile corresponded to a cut-off point of 22 raw scores, and the first level was created for respondents scoring between 11 and 21, who were categorized as having Minimal Negative Beliefs (NB), indicating low disagreement or concern regarding arranged marriage. The 50th percentile rank was equal to a raw score of 28, which corresponded to a raw score range of 22 to 27, labeled as Moderate Negative Beliefs, reflecting a balanced or undecided perspective. Scores from 28 to 34 represented Strong Negative Beliefs, corresponding to the 75th percentile, suggesting a high level of concern, while those scoring 35 to 55 were grouped under Firm Negative Beliefs, corresponding to the 100th percentile, showing very strong opposition or dissatisfaction toward the concept of arranged marriage. A one-way ANOVA was conducted on the levels of NBAM, which revealed a significant difference in each level. Frequency distribution also supported that each level of NBAM had a sufficient number of participants with discrete categorization. This categorization provides a simple and balanced interpretation of participants' responses based on equal numerical divisions, rather than sample-based distribution.

Table 9

Cut-off Scores and Levels of Positive Beliefs About Arranged Marriage (PBAM)

Raw Scores	Range	Percentile	Level	<i>f</i> (%)
<26	8-25	<25	Minimal PB	64(20)
30	26 – 29	50	Moderate PB	73(23)
33	30 – 32	75	Strong PB	78(25)
>33	33-40	>75	Firm PB	97(31)

Note. PB= positive beliefs

Table 9 displays how PBAM (Positive Subscale) scores relate to different levels of acceptance of arranged marriage, with breakdowns for both males and females. For both genders, people who score below 13 have minimal positive beliefs, meaning they have the least positive views on arranged marriage, placing them below the 25th percentile. Those with scores between 26 and 29 fall into the moderate positive beliefs, which reflects an average

level of acceptance, around the 50th percentile. Scores between 30 and 32 represent strong positive beliefs, indicating more positive beliefs about arranged marriage, with these individuals in the 75th percentile. Finally, people with scores above 33 show firm positive beliefs, meaning they have a very strong belief in arranged marriage, and fall into the top 25% of the sample. A one-way ANOVA further confirmed the clear categorization of the levels of positive beliefs. Similarly, the frequency distribution showed an almost fair number of participants in each category.

Discussion

This study developed and validated the Negative and Positive Beliefs About Arranged Marriage Questionnaire (NPBAM-Q), a tool made to understand how people in Pakistan think and feel about arranged marriages. The results showed that people often hold both positive and negative beliefs at the same time some believe arranged marriages bring family support, respect, and stability, while others worry about emotional distance, lack of choice, and pressure. Factor analysis confirmed these two sets of beliefs as separate but strongly supported structures, with high loadings and strong reliability ($\alpha = .86$ for positive beliefs and $\alpha = .90$ for negative beliefs). The correlation between the two was negative ($r = -.26$), meaning when someone had strong positive beliefs, they were less likely to hold negative ones, and vice versa.

Gender differences were especially noticeable while both males and females had almost similar positive beliefs, females reported significantly higher negative beliefs compared to males, and the difference was statistically significant which reflects the added social pressure and emotional burden that women may face in arranged marriages. The findings reveal that women in Pakistani culture tend to hold more negative beliefs about arranged marriage compared to men, a difference deeply influenced by social, cultural, and gender-based factors. Previous research supports this, showing that Pakistani women often experience limited autonomy and face traditional gender role expectations, along with considerable family pressure. These factors collectively contribute to their more negative attitudes toward arranged marriage. For instance, Mirza and Jenkins (2004) found that Pakistani women suffer from psychological distress at rates two to three times higher than men, largely due to gender discrimination and related social stressors. Such pressures frequently persist after marriage, where women are expected to conform to traditional domestic roles and protect family honor. Moreover, women's restricted involvement in selecting their spouses and societal expectations for obedience can foster resentment and skepticism toward arranged marriages (Zakar et al., 2012). Ali et al. (2020) emphasizes that when women lack a say in marital decisions, it negatively affects their mental well-being and their outlook on marriage. Additionally, entrenched societal norms often place men as household heads and decision-makers, while women remain in subordinate roles, further reinforcing an imbalance of power within marriages (Ali et al., 2011).

The overall NPBAM-Q structure matched well with the Social Exchange Theory (Homans, 1958), which explains how people make decisions based on costs and benefits many accept the limitations of arranged marriage in exchange for family harmony and support. However, the modern generation especially educated youth is more likely to question these trade-offs, showing how tradition and modernity are now clashing.

Limitations and Suggestions

The sample in this study mainly consisted of young and educated individuals, which may influence the findings, especially about age and life experience. Although the data were collected from a diverse population, the reliance on convenience sampling still limits the generalizability of the results. Future research should consider including participants from varied marital statuses, particularly married individuals, to better understand how real-life experiences shape marriage-related beliefs. Furthermore, a deeper comprehension of the societal and individual elements impacting marital attitudes may be provided by comparing opinions regarding arranged and love marriages using the same validated instrument.

Implications and Recommendations

The Negative and Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage Questionnaire (NPBAM-Q) can be a valuable tool for therapists working with individuals who are either thinking about marriage or navigating marriage-related challenges. It offers a way to better understand a person's thoughts, expectations, and concerns, especially when emotional and cultural factors are shaping their decisions. This can be particularly helpful for young adults who may feel torn or confused as they face pressure or uncertainty around marriage choices. In counseling sessions, the NPBAM-Q can open the door to meaningful conversations and help guide more balanced, thoughtful decision-

making. Beyond therapy, the questionnaire also holds promise for cultural research. In societies like Pakistan, where arranged marriage is deeply rooted in tradition, the NPBAM-Q can help researchers explore how beliefs around marriage are shaped by shared values, customs, and social expectations. This can lead to a deeper understanding of how cultural norms influence personal choices and attitudes toward marriage.

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Appendix

Negative and Positive Beliefs about Arranged Marriage Questionnaire (NPBAM-Q)

ہدایات
یہ پیمانہ آپ کے ارینج میریج سے متعلق خیالات اور عقائد جاننے کے لیے تیار کیا گیا ہے۔ براہ کرم ہر بیان کو غور سے پڑھیں اور اس کے بارے میں اپنی رائے کا اظہار کریں۔ یاد رکھیں کہ اس میں کوئی درست یا غلط جواب نہیں ہے، اس لیے پوری ایمانداری سے صرف اپنے ذاتی خیالات اور محسوسات کے مطابق جواب دیں۔
براہ کرم ہر بیان کا لازمی طور پر جواب دیں۔ ہر بیان کے جواب کے لیے درج ذیل درجہ بندی استعمال کریں۔

بالکل متفق

متفق

غیر جانبدار / نہ متفق نہ غیر متفق

غیر متفق

بالکل غیر متفق

آپ سے گزارش ہے کہ ہر بیان کو غور سے پڑھ کر اس کے مطابق ایک درجہ کا انتخاب کریں جو آپ کی رائے کی بہترین ترجمانی کرے۔

ارینج میریج کے بارے میں منفی عقائد

Sr.#	Statements	بالکل غیر متفق	غیر متفق	غیر جانبدار	متفق	بالکل متفق
1	ارینج میریج میں زندگی اپنی مرضی سے نہیں گزارا جا سکتی ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5
2	ارینج میریج میں زندگی مشکل ہوتی ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5
3	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ایک دوسرے سے مطابقت نہیں رکھتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
4	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ہر بات شیئر نہیں کر سکتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
5	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ایک دوسرے کا ساتھ نہیں دیتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
6	ارینج میریج میں ایک طرفہ کوششیں زیادہ ہوتی ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
7	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی مجبوری میں ساتھ رہتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
8	ارینج میریج میں ذہنی سکون کم ہوتا ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5
9	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ایک دوسرے کو قبول نہیں کرتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
10	ارینج میریج صرف خاندان والوں کو خوش رکھنے کے لیے کی جاتی ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5
11	ارینج میریج میں لڑائی جھگڑے زیادہ ہوتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5

ارینج میریج کے بارے میں مثبت عقائد

Sr. #	Item Statement	بالکل غیر متفق	غیر متفق	غیر جانبدار	متفق	بالکل متفق
1	ارینج میریج میں گھر والوں کا ساتھ ہوتا ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5
2	ارینج میریج زیادہ کامیاب ہوتی ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5
3	ارینج میریج میں زندگی زیادہ اچھی گزرتی ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5
4	والدین اپنی اولاد کے لئے صحیح جیون ساتھی تلاش کرتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
5	ارینج میریج تمام پہلوؤں کو دیکھ کر کی جاتی ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5
6	ارینج میریج میں میاں بیوی ایک دوسرے کا زیادہ احترام کرتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
7	ارینج میریج میں خاندانی رسم و رواج پروان چڑھتے ہیں۔	1	2	3	4	5
8	ارینج میریج میں ماں باپ کی عزت زیادہ کی جاتی ہے۔	1	2	3	4	5